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Advancing Therapeutics through Smart Polymeric Complex Systems

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ABSTRACT

Polyelectrolyte complexation has gained significant attention as an effective and versatile approach in the development of advanced pharmaceutical and biomedical systems. Formed through electrostatic interactions between oppositely charged polymers, these complexes offer unique physicochemical properties that support diverse therapeutic applications. The formation and stability of such systems are influenced by various factors, including pH, ionic strength, polymer concentration, molecular weight, and charge ratio. Based on their structural and functional characteristics, polyelectrolyte complexes can be classified into different types for specific biomedical purposes. Their mechanism of formation enables efficient drug encapsulation, sustained release, targeted delivery, and improved therapeutic efficacy. In addition to drug delivery, their applications extend to gene delivery, tissue engineering, wound healing, and vaccine formulations. Owing to advantages such as biocompatibility, biodegradability, and ease of preparation, polyelectrolyte complexation represents a promising strategy for designing innovative and efficient therapeutic systems.

Keywords:- Polyelectrolyte complex; Polyelectrolytes; PEC mechanism; Applications; Evaluation

INTRODUCTION

Polyelectrolyte complex are the complexes formed due to the electrostatic interaction of oppositely charged particles or polymers, when dissolved in the polar solvents i.e. water, acetone, methanol etc. The interaction involves a polymeric cationic group interacting with a polymeric anionic group which results in the phase separation [1]. PECs are ideal for their high drug stability, solubility, and control release. These also have low toxicity levels and high recyclability potential and also contain self-healing properties. Polyelectrolytes are polymers with ionizable functional groups. These functional groups are amine-based for polycations, and carboxylic group based for polyanions [2]. These PECs are also known as poly salts as it exhibits similar behavior to both the polymers like high molecular weight compounds as well as the electrolyte salts [3].

PECs can be obtained by changing the chemical structure of polymers, such as molecular weight, flexibility, functional group structure, charge density, hydrophilicity and hydrophobicity, as well as reaction conditions like pH, ionic strength, concentration, mixing ratio and temperature. PECs play a different type of uses like coating on films and fibers, implants for medical use, microcapsules, films, hydrogels, also used in pharmaceutical industries in binding the products as catalysts and isolation of nucleic acids and fractionation of proteins. The interactions between anionic and cationic charged proteins enhances functional properties like foaming and aggregation phenomena or gelation. The interactions and amount of precipitation vary depending on the concentration of different protein in the mixture, the ionic strength and pH of the solution [4].

POLYELECTROLYTES

The polymers which contain a net negative or positive charge at near

neutral pH are said to be polyelectrolytes. Their solubility is by the electrostatic interactions between water and the charged monomer. Examples of those polymers includes DNA, protein, natural gums, certain derivatives of cellulose polymers and carrageenan [1]. Structure of the compound is dominated by hydrogen bonding, ion dipole forces, and hydrophobic interactions and the main attractive forces are electrostatic interaction [3]. Pectin carrageenan, alginates, and carboxymethyl cellulose are used in the foods [4].

CLASSIFICATION OF POLYELECTROLYTES

Based on origin

Natural Polyelectrolytes: These are obtained from the renewable resources like animals, plants, and microorganisms these includes the polymers like Carrageenan's (anionic, derived from the red algae) Hyaluronic Acid (present in glycosaminoglycan in the extracellular matrix and synovial fluid), alginate, albumin, proteins, guar gum. These are non-toxic in nature and easily biodegradable in nature and have swelling property which helps in the controlled release of the drugs [5].

Synthetic Polyelectrolytes: These are obtained from the synthetic processes, which also contains polymer chains that gets electrically charged when dissolved in the solvents water it includes Diallyl dimethyl ammonium chloride, Polyacrylic Acid, Poly sulfonates, polyethyleimine [6].

Chemically Modified Polyelectrolytes: These are obtained from the chemical modification of the natural neutral compounds or polymers. Chitosan (derived from chitin containing positive charge), pectin, cellulose based derivatives etc., [1].

Based on electrochemistry

Anionic Polyelectrolytes: These are also known as polyanionic polymers. These polymers contain numerous anionic

charges within the structure. It includes DNA, Heparin, Nitrate (No₂), Hydrogen sulphate (Hso₄), Hydroxide (OH), Poly(methacrylic acid) (PMAA) [1]. Carboxylic groups like alginate pectin, collagen, polyacrylic acid [4].

Cationic Polyelectrolytes: These are also known as polycationic polymers. These polymers contain numerous cationic charges within the structure. It includes Nucleic acids, alginase, carrageenan, Hydronium ion(H₃o⁺), Ammonia ion (NH₄⁺) [1].

MECHANISM OF FORMATION OF POLYELECTROLYTE COMPLEX:

Formation of the PECs involves interpolymer interactions, like dipole interactions, Van der Waals forces, H-bonding and Hydrophobic interactions. The steps involved in the formation of the poly electrolyte complex can be represented as three steps.

Step 1: Primary Complex Formation

It is the first step in the formation of the PEC; it takes place by the coulombs force. This is a rapid process in which the mixing of the oppositely charged particles takes place.

Step 2: Formation of new bonds with in intracomplex and correction of distortions of polymer chains

It is the second step in the formation of the polyelectrolyte complexes. It involves intra complexation often resulting in new bond formation or polymer chain corrections.

Step 3: Inter complex Aggregation

The final step results in inter-aggregations by the help of hydrophobic interactions[1].

TYPES OF POLYELECTROLYTES COMPLEXS

Natural-Natural Polymer Complex:

These are the complex compounds that are formed by the interaction of two or more natural polymers these includes proteins polynucleotides and polysaccharides. Chitosan has been used for the preparation

of various polyelectrolyte complex products with natural polyanions as carboxymethyl cellulose, alginic acid, dextran sulfate, carboxymethyl dextran, heparin, carrageenan, pectin, and Xanthane [4].

Natural-Synthetic Polymer Complex:

These are the complex compounds that are formed by the combination of both natural and synthetic polymers which are mainly used for the enhancement of the drug delivery and tissue engineering. The interaction between proteins and synthetic polyelectrolytes was investigated using techniques like turbidity and quasilastic light-scattering [4]

Synthetic-Synthetic Polymer Complex:

These are the complex compounds that are formed by the interaction of two or more synthetic polymers like Nylon-6,6 Polyester-Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET).

Formation of polyelectrolyte complex between synthetic polymers was done using conductometric, potentiometric or turbidimetric titration [4].

Protein-Polyelectrolyte Complexation:

These are the complexes formed by the interaction of the protein with the oppositely charged polyelectrolytes. This process is seen in the chromosomes in the body [5].

APPLICATIONS OF PEC

Used as membranes for coating on films tablets and also used in the sustained release tablets and in some of drug delivery systems as it also has an advantage of the controlled released medication by having high solubility properties and also used as binding agent, in food industries, isolation nucleic acid and fractionation of proteins, for binding pharmaceutical products and for the drug delivery of microcapsules and commonly used in the cosmetics [1]. These are also used in the medical preparation of the ophthalmic and transdermal drug delivery systems. These are also widely used in the

antiviral and anti-bacterial therapy.

These can be used to stabilize colloidal suspensions, or to initiate precipitation of the product. They can also be used to impart a surface charge to neutral particles, enabling them to be dispersed in aqueous solution. These are mainly used as thickeners, emulsifiers, conditioners, flocculants. They are used in water treatment. Used in the preparation of soaps, shampoos, and cosmetics. These helps in oral drug delivery, human periodontal ligaments matrix, dermal wound healing, targeted drug release in intestinal colon, and also delivery of drugs in subcutaneous route. In the pharmaceutical industries, for controlled drug delivery [4].

Polyelectrolyte complex Drug Delivery System

Polyelectrolyte complexes are commonly explored for delivering medicines in the body. They can hold therapeutic compounds within their structure and release them gradually over time. This helps protect sensitive drugs from degradation and improves their effectiveness in treatment. Such systems are widely studied in Pharmaceutical Sciences for developing controlled and targeted drug delivery methods.

Polyelectrolyte complex Gene Delivery system

Polyelectrolyte complexes (PECs), such as chitosan-DNA PECs, are non-viral vectors for gene therapy. They are effective for the transport of genetic materials such as DNA and siRNA into the cell with good transfection efficiency. Lyophilization is used for the stabilization and concentration of the PECs by preventing degradation and aggregation [7].

Tissue Engineering of Polyelectrolyte complex

In Tissue Engineering, polyelectrolyte complexes are used to design scaffold-like

structures that support cell attachment and growth. These scaffolds provide a suitable environment for cells to regenerate damaged tissues, which can assist in the repair of skin, cartilage, and bone [8].

Water Purification of Polyelectrolyte complex

Another important use of PECs is in water treatment. They can interact with pollutants such as dyes, heavy metals, and suspended particles, helping to remove them from contaminated water. Because of this capability, PEC-based materials are studied in Environmental Engineering for improving purification processes [9].

Food Industry Applications

In Food Science, polyelectrolyte complexes are used to encapsulate nutrients, vitamins, and flavour compounds. Encapsulation helps protect these ingredients from environmental damage and allows their gradual release, which can enhance the stability and quality of food products [10]

Protective Coatings and Films

PECs can form thin films that are applied as protective layers on different materials. These coatings may improve resistance to corrosion, enhance durability, and contribute to the development of biodegradable packaging materials [11].

FACTORS INFLUENCING THE FORMATION OF PEC's

The factor influencing PEC formation are nature of charged particle, charge density, temperature, molecular weight, ionic strength, pH, Other factors include Chain flexibility Polydispersity (PDI), Polyelectrolyte concentration, charge stoichiometry, mixing order, mixing speed and duration [2]. Degree of substitution, nature of the solvents [4].

Ionic strength

Increase in the ionic strength leads to

decrease in the average diameter and may increase the chain flexibility [12]. If ionic strength is too strong, then formation of precipitation may occur [13]. Ionic strength is the concentration of ions in the solution. It affects the electrostatic interactions between the charged groups in the polyelectrolytes. It can influence the formation of complexes.

Charge distribution on the PEs

Polyelectrolytes contain repeating units with ionizable groups that dissociate in solution, producing charged sites along the polymer chain. This results in a distribution of positive or negative charges along the backbone, influencing interactions with solvents, ions, and other molecules [14].

Density of the PEs

The quantity of mass or charge per unit volume of the polymer is referred to as the density of polyelectrolytes. It influences characteristics like swelling, solubility, and interaction with other molecules and is dependent on the number of ionizable groups along the polymer chain [14].

Charges

Along their polymer chain, polyelectrolytes have several ionizable groups that separate in solution and produce charges. Depending on the functional groups that are present, these charges can be either positive (polycations) or negative (polyanions) [15].

PE chain stiffness

PE chain stiffness is defined as the stiffness of the polyelectrolyte chain due to electrostatic repulsion between similar charges along the polymer backbone. As a result, the chain is stretched and less flexible in solution [16].

Concentration

Concentration refers to the amount of

polyelectrolyte present in the solution. It influences the interaction between the polymer chains. It also influences properties like viscosity, expansion of the chains, and electrostatic interactions [14].

Strength of the ionic sites

Strength of ionic sites refers to how strongly the ionizable groups on the polymer chain dissociate and hold their charge in solution. Strong ionic sites ionize completely, while weak ionic sites ionize only partially depending on the pH of the solution [14].

Mixing ratio

The term mixing ratio is used to denote the proportion in which different polyelectrolytes, like polycations and polyanions, are mixed in solution [14].

Duration and intensity

The term "duration" refers to the time provided for polyelectrolytes to interact and complex. The term "intensity" refers to the level of mixing or agitation [16].

Chain flexibility

Chain flexibility is defined as the ability of the polyelectrolyte polymer chain to rotate or bend in solution. It affects the conformation, interaction, and complex formation of the polymer [17].

Molecular weight

The term "molecular weight" is used to indicate the total weight of the polymer chain, which consists of repeating units. Polyelectrolytes with higher molecular weight have longer chains, and this may influence viscosity, chain entanglements, and complex formation [17].

Polymer structure

The structure of polymer refers to the arrangement of the monomer units and ionic groups in the polymer chain. This structure affects the shape, flexibility, and interaction of the polymer [17].

Hydrophobicity

Hydrophobicity means that some segments of the polymer chain tend to repel water. Hydrophobic groups in polyelectrolytes can affect their conformation, aggregation, and interactions with other molecules in solution [16].

Temperature conditions during process

Temperature during the process is also significant in terms of affecting the mobility of polymer chains and the interaction rate between polyelectrolytes. Temperature changes might influence complex formation, stability, and solubility [16].

Degree of complexation

Degree of complexation is used to measure the level of interaction and binding of oppositely charged polyelectrolytes to form a complex. It is affected by factors such as charge density, ratio of mixing, and ionic strength of the solution [14].

pH

The pH influences the ionization of the functional groups in the polyelectrolyte chain. Changes in pH can result in changes in the charges of the polymer, hence solubility, conformation, and complex formation [14].

ADVANTAGES OF POLYELECTROLYTE COMPLEX

It is generally non-toxic, which makes the complexes useful in biomedical and pharmaceutical applications. The process of forming these complexes is fast, simple, and, in most cases, does not involve the use of harmful chemicals. They are effective in the controlled release of drugs through the regulation of the interactions between the polymers. They are relatively inexpensive, mainly because the process of preparation is simple, as are the materials used in the process. They are biodegradable, which makes them safe for the environment, as they are easily broken

down without leaving behind harmful residues. They are also less likely to be incompatible with the human body, which makes them useful in drug delivery systems [18].

EVALUATION OF POLYELECTROLYTE COMPLEX pH

The pH test for electrolyte complexes is defined as the measurement of the hydrogen ion concentration in the system. This test is used to assess the ionization of the charged groups in the complex. The test is also used to understand the effect of the pH on the complex.

Degree of substitution

0.2 g of LBG polymers are solubilized in 50 ml 0.01 N HCL and 2 drops of phenolphthalein was added to the solution as indicator, then the solution was titrated with 0.1 M NaOH solution, the volume of the titrant after the change in color was noted down.

FTIR Spectroscopy

FTIR spectra ($4000-400\text{ cm}^{-1}$) of LBG and CMLG samples were recorded using FTIR spectrophotometer to confirm structural modification.

Viscosity

The polymer dispersion was prepared by addition of 250 mg of the CMLG derivative into 50ml of water and stirred for 20 minutes at 500 rpm with magnetic stirrer. Now it is placed under the Brook field viscometer with spindle number 64 at different rpm of 10, 30, 50, 100 and the viscosity reading was recorded.

NMR (Nuclear magnetic resonance)

Nuclear Magnetic Resonance spectroscopy in Polyelectrolyte Complexes is a method for structural analysis. This method is based on the analysis of the behavior of an atom in a magnetic field. This method is useful for identifying the composition and

confirming the complex formation.

SEM (Scanning electron microscopy)

Scanning Electron Microscopy is a method that allows us to examine the surface of a material in detail by using a beam of electrons to produce a detailed image of its surface morphology and structure. It gives us information about texture, shape, and particle size.

DSC (Differential scanning calorimetry)

Differential Scanning Calorimetry in Polyelectrolyte Complexes is a method for measuring the change of heat with temperature. DSC is useful for identifying the melting point of a polymer and for ascertaining the interaction of two polymers.

TGA (Thermogravimetric analysis)

Thermogravimetric Analysis of Polyelectrolyte Complexes: Thermogravimetric Analysis, or TGA, is a method that is used to measure the changes that take place in the weight of a substance while increasing its temperature.

X – ray diffractometry

X-ray Diffraction (XRD) in Polyelectrolyte Complexes is an analytical technique used to study the crystalline structure of the complexes. It works by measuring the diffraction pattern of X rays passing through the material. This helps determine the degree of crystallinity and structural changes after complex formation.

**PHYSICOCHEMICAL
CHARACTERISTICS**

Particle size and distribution – In the context of polyelectrolyte complexes, the term "particle size distribution" is used to denote the measurement and analysis of the sizes present in a given complex. This term is important in that it defines whether the complex is uniform in size or varies in size.

Surface charge (zeta potential) – Zeta potential or surface charge in polyelectrolyte complexes is the electrical potential at the interface between the charged complex and the surrounding environment. This is an indication of the net surface charge due to the interaction of oppositely charged polymers. This is used as a means to evaluate the stability of the complex formed, with higher values implying higher stability.

Morphology – It is defined as the study of the shape, surface structure, and physical appearance of the complexes formed. This is usually carried out through tests such as electron microscopy to identify factors such as their size, surface features, and structural homogeneity, which affect their overall performance.

Solubility and swelling behavior – Solubility in polyelectrolyte complexes is defined as the capacity of the polyelectrolyte complex to dissolve in a solvent, depending on various factors such as polymer composition and pH of the medium. Swelling behavior in polyelectrolyte complexes is defined as the capacity of polyelectrolyte complexes to absorb fluids and increase in volume, depending on various factors such as ionic interactions and environmental conditions.

Mechanical properties – They imply the ability of the material to withstand physical properties without any deformity or collapse. This includes properties like strength, elasticity, flexibility, and rigidity. These properties are affected by the interactions of the polymers and the overall conditions. They play a critical role in the integrity of the material.

CONCLUSION

Polyelectrolyte complexes have emerged as promising multifunctional systems in pharmaceutical and biomedical sciences due to their ability to form through

electrostatic interactions between oppositely charged polymers. Their formation and performance are influenced by several factors, including pH, ionic strength, charge density, molecular weight, and polymer ratio, which directly affect stability and functionality. Based on composition and interaction pattern, PECs can be classified into various types and tailored for specific purposes. The mechanism of complexation enables efficient encapsulation, controlled drug release, and improved bioavailability. PECs have found broad applications in drug delivery, tissue engineering, gene delivery, wound healing, and vaccine formulations. Their major advantages include biocompatibility, biodegradability, ease of preparation, and enhanced therapeutic efficiency. Proper evaluation through physicochemical and biological characterization ensures quality and performance. Overall, PECs represent an innovative and adaptable approach for future therapeutic advancements.

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